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Parental Involvement And Fatalistic Belief As Correlates Of Adolescents' Psycho-Social Development In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the parental involvement and fatalistic belief as correlates of adolescents' psycho-social development in Anambra State. The correlational survey research design was adopted in the study. The population of the study comprises 21,272 senior secondary school students in 269 public senior secondary schools in Anambra State, while purposive sample method was used to reduce the population, and got 350 as the sample size. A researcher developed instrument duly validated by three experts was used for data collection. The data was collected using a structured questionnaire structured by the researcher for the study. The data was analysed using multiple regression analysis and ANOVA as a statistical technique. The study found that Parental involvement has significant influence on with adolescent's psycho-social development in Anambra State ($F, 4.205, P, 0.001$). Fatalistic belief has significant influence on with adolescent's psycho-social development Anambra State ($F, 8.163, P, 0.000$). The study recommended that The findings of the study have proven that fatalistic belief positively correlates with identity crisis and adolescents. Thus, it is recommended that cognitive restructuring should be used by counselling psychologists to reshape the cognition and demystify the fatalistic beliefs among adolescents. It is recommended that parents should get more involved in the socio-emotional development of their children by building up relationship that involves listening and empathising with their children, validating their emotions, teaching them how to regulate their feelings and teaching them how to solve problems which will help adolescents to feel that their parents are physically and emotionally engaged in helping them to figure out their weaknesses and how to overcome identity related problem thereby drastically reducing identity crisis.

Keywords: parental involvement, fatalistic belief, adolescents' psycho-social development, Anambra State

INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a critical stage of human growth characterized by rapid physical, emotional, cognitive, and social transitions that shape personality and future behavior. During this period, adolescents encounter developmental tasks such as identity formation, emotional regulation, value orientation, peer relationship management, and autonomy from parents (Balogun, 2023). These processes are collectively referred to as psycho-social development, and they significantly determine how young people integrate into society, pursue education, engage in productive activities, and relate to others. In Nigeria, particularly in Anambra State, adolescents face unique developmental challenges arising from socio-cultural practices, economic uncertainties, family dynamics, and traditional belief systems that either support or

hinder their growth. Among the critical factors influencing adolescent psycho-social development are parental involvement and fatalistic beliefs (Singh, & Mahajan, 2021).

Parental involvement encompasses the degree to which parents actively engage in their children's education, emotional life, and moral upbringing. It includes practices such as monitoring academic performance, providing guidance, communicating expectations, offering emotional support, and modeling appropriate social behaviors (Adeyeye, 2023). Studies have shown that adolescents whose parents are actively involved in their lives tend to exhibit higher self-esteem, resilience, better academic outcomes, and healthier interpersonal relationships. Conversely, low parental involvement is often linked to maladjustment, deviant behaviors, emotional instability, and difficulty in coping with societal pressures (Alimba, Aguocha, & Uchunor, 2024). On the other hand, fatalistic belief—a common worldview in many African societies refers to the perception that events in life are predetermined, inevitable, and beyond individual control. In Anambra State, where traditional religious practices, cultural values, and sometimes misinterpreted spiritual ideologies coexist with modern education and globalization, fatalism can strongly influence adolescent attitudes. Adolescents who hold strong fatalistic beliefs may view success or failure as the result of destiny rather than personal effort. This orientation can discourage initiative, weaken motivation for achievement, and reduce problem-solving abilities, thereby affecting psycho-social development. However, in some cases, fatalistic beliefs may also provide a sense of comfort and resilience in the face of hardship, illustrating its dual influence (Anierobi, 2022).

The interplay between parental involvement and fatalistic belief in shaping adolescents' psycho-social development has not been sufficiently explored in Anambra State. While existing research has examined parental influence on education and behavior, and others have studied belief systems in shaping worldview, few have combined these variables to understand how they correlate with adolescents' ability to navigate the challenges of growing up. (Anierobi, Nwikpo, Okeke, & Ezennaka, 2024). This is significant because the youth population constitutes a large proportion of Anambra State's demographic, and their psycho-social adjustment has implications for education, crime rates, social cohesion, and future leadership. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate parental involvement and fatalistic belief as correlates of adolescents' psycho-social development in Anambra State. By examining these relationships, the study aims to provide empirical evidence that will guide parents, educators, counselors, and policymakers in fostering positive developmental outcomes among adolescents.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to ascertain the parental involvement and fatalistic belief as correlates of adolescents' psycho-social development in Anambra State

. Specially, the study sought to:

1. Ascertain the relationship between parental involvement and adolescent's psycho-social development in Anambra State.
2. Find out the relationship between fatalistic belief and adolescent's psycho-social development in Anambra State

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Fatalistic Belief

Fatalistic belief is a family of related philosophical doctrines that stress the subjugation of all events or actions to fate or destiny, and is commonly associated with the consequent attitude of resignation in the face of future events which are thought to be inevitable (Anyaeji, & Ndukwe, 2023). While the terms are sometimes used interchangeably, fatalism, determinism, and pre-determinism are distinct, as each emphasises a different aspect of the futility of human will or the foreordination of destiny. However, all these doctrines share common ground. Determinists generally agree that human actions affect the future but that human action is itself determined by a causal chain of prior events. Their view does not accentuate a "submission" to fate or destiny, whereas fatalists stress an acceptance of future events as inevitable. Determinists believe the future is fixed specifically due to causality; fatalists and pre-

determinists believe that some or all aspects of the future are inescapable but, for fatalists, not necessarily due to causality (Anyaeji, & Ndukwe, 2023).

Fatalistic belief is a loser term than determinism. The presence of historical "indeterminists" or chances, i.e. events that could not be predicted by sole knowledge of other events, is an idea still compatible with fatalism. Necessity (such as a law of nature) will happen just as inevitably as a chance both can be imagined as sovereign. According to Chikendu, R. E. (2023). fatalistic beliefs usually emerge when individuals are confronted with complex situations such as risks or accidents. To analyse and cope with such situations, people mostly rely on their beliefs to compensate for their lack of knowledge about the causal factors of such complex situations. Therefore, 'an understanding of the beliefs people hold about risks and the causes of accidents as well as their perceptions of risk targets and the need for safety, are important prerequisites for effectively managing risk and designing preventive measures' (Kouabenan, 2019).

Parental Involvement

Parenting is a critical aspect of child upbringing in every family and society. Hence, family is the smallest unit that constitutes the society. What comes up as a result of this training affects the society either positively or negatively due to the time young children spend in the presence of their parents, it seems logical to conclude that the family environment has a marked influence on their lives (Nwokolo, & Obijindu, 2020). Through interactions with their parents, children become aware of the consequences of their actions and of others' expectations of them. This early socialisation process therefore, appears to be a means by which children come to internalise a sense of what is right and of what is wrong (Enemu, & Onyenwe, 2023).

According to Lone, (2022). parental involvement encompasses acts of parenthood, the child upbringing, training and rearing or child education. Parents world over, are in search of greener pastures, and for some decades, there has been a drift of families from their place of origin. Nwogbo (2023) describe parental involvement as the activities occurring between a parent and a child or between a parent and teachers at school that may contribute to the child's educational outcomes and development. According to NCLB (2021), parental involvement is a regular participation of parents, a two-way process, and meaningful communication involving student academic learning and other school activities including: (a) Assisting their child's learning; (b) Being actively involved in their child's education at school; (c) Serving as full partners in their child's education and being included, as appropriate, in decision-making and on advisory committees to assist in the education of their child; and (d) The carrying out of other activities such as those described in section 1118 of the ESEA" Section 9101(32).

Theoretical Framework

Social Identity Theory by Tajfel's (1979)

Social identity theory was developed by Tajfel's (1979) and postulated that a person's sense of who they are based on their group membership(s) and the groups (e.g. social class, family, football team etc.) which one belongs to were an important source of pride and self-esteem. He further stated that groups give one a sense of social identity: a sense of belonging to the social world. In order to increase our self-image, one needs to enhance the status of the group to which one belongs to. Tajfel and Turner (1979) stated that there are three mental processes involved in evaluating one identity in the context of group one belonging to "us" or "them" (i.e. "in-group" and "out-group"). These take place in a particular order. The first is categorization. According to Tajfel and Turner (1979), one can categorise objects in order to understand them and identify them. In a very similar way we categorise people (including ourselves) in order to understand the social environment. One can use social categories like black, white, Australian, Christian, Muslim, student, and bus driver because they are useful.

If individuals can assign people to a category then that tells us things about those people, and as individuals saw with the bus driver example, individuals couldn't function in a normal manner without using these categories; i.e. in the context of the bus. Similarly, find out things about ourselves by knowing what categories individuals belong to. Individuals define appropriate behaviour by reference to the norms

of groups individuals belong to, but you can only do this if you can tell who belongs to your group. An individual can belong to many different groups. In the second stage, social identification, individuals adopt the identity of the group individuals have categorised themselves as belonging to. If for example you have categorized yourself as a student, the chances are you will adopt the identity of a student and begin to act in the ways you believe students act (and conform to the norms of the group).

There will be an emotional significance to your identification with a group, and your self-esteem will become bound up with group membership. The final stage is social comparison. Once individuals have categorised themselves as part of a group and have identified with that group, individuals then tend to compare that group with other groups. If one's self-esteem is to be maintained our group needs to compare favourably with other groups. This is critical to understanding prejudice, because once two groups identify themselves as rivals, they are forced to compete in order for the members to maintain their self-esteem. Competition and hostility between groups is thus not only a matter of competing for resources (like in Sherif's Robbers Cave) like jobs but also the result of competing identities.

Review of Empirical Studies

Musa & Aisha (2025) aim of this study was to explore the effect of family socio-economic status (occupation) on students' academic Achievement. Descriptive survey research design was employed. Systematic methods of review were using by sourcing both primary and secondary data particularly documentary sources. Thematic analysis used in describing the related empirical studies. Occupation is widely recognized as a critical factor influencing an individual's social and economic success, as it provides a pathway to improved opportunities and a better quality of life. Nigeria is a nation with people that are classified on the basis of socio-economic status. These classes are high, middle and low socio-economic status. This class or division has implication for the type of school a child goes to in Nigeria. Privates' high schools are restricted to special family only. It was discovered by this research that rich parents can spends more than the poor parents and that investment may lead to better outcomes for their children. It also learnt that poverty alone does not account for all the difference in the performance of the students. The paper recommends among others to encourage and involve parents from all socio-economic backgrounds in their children's education. Provide opportunities for parents to establish effective communication channels to bridge the gap between lower class and high class of parents.

Akindipe (2025) examined the impact of parental involvement intervention on students' math achievement and self-efficacy. The sample consisted of 51 fifth grade students recruited from 2 private schools in the Lagos educational district III that chose to participate in the study. Comprising 17 boys and 34 girls with an average age of 10.89 years, students from one of the schools served as the intervention group while the second school was the control group. The intervention group underwent home structure, parental supervision, and school-home communication intervention while the control group did not. Collected data was analyzed using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) and independent t-test analyses. Results showed that the intervention significantly improved students' math achievement but not math self-efficacy. Educational implications of the results are discussed

Salihu, (2025) determine the influence of parental involvement on academic performance of students of Arabic studies in North Central. Descriptive research design was adopted for this research. Purposive random sampling technique was used to select 25 parents from each of the five selected schools. Two research questions were raised and answered. Self-made questionnaire was used to collect relevant data. Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics of simple percentage, frequency count, mean and standard deviation. Results revealed that parental involvement significantly influences academic performance of students of Arabic studies. it was recommended that parents and learners should be educated to recognize the significance of parental involvement on overall academic performance of the learners.

Ughamadu, Okaforcha, & Igboanugo, (2025) examined parental involvement as predictors of students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study while two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted correlational

research design. The population of the study was 21,272 SS2 students in 267 public secondary schools in the six education zones in Anambra State. The sample of 1,064 SS2 students was used for the study. Multistage sampling procedure comprising proportionate stratified and simple random sampling techniques were used for the study. The instrument 'Parental Involvement Questionnaire (PIQ)' was used for data collection while Students' Academic Performance Scores (SAPS) was used to measure students' academic performance for this study. The instrument was subjected to face and construct validation. Face validation was done by three experts. On the other hand, construct validation was carried out by Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with the help SPSS version 26 which indicated that the instrument was suitable for the study. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha Coefficient method and the average coefficient of 0.78 for PIQ was obtained. Direct method of data administration was utilized by the researcher together with five research assistants. Out of 1,064 copies of the instrument administered, 935(88%) of the instrument were correctly completed and returned. Simple linear regression statistical tool was used for the study. The findings of the study revealed that parental involvement in school decision-making and parenting practices positively and significantly predict students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Esho, Ibitoye, Iyanda, & Okoku,(2025). reveals the effect produced by the participation of parents on the mathematics achievement in correlation with solving chemistry problems in Ilesa East Local Government Area, Osun State, Nigeria. A total number of 1500 students were used in this present study, with their age ranged from 12 to 18 years. It has been revealed that only 11.0% acknowledged involvement of parents in academic discussions regularly, showing a significance study gap in support for students' mathematics education. Furthermore, there is wide variation in which students confidently approach chemistry problems through the use of mathematical skills, with 35.9% showing strong anxiety about their skills, this is expressing that a lack of assistance correlates with poor self-assessment and increased stress related to applying mathematics in chemistry. The data from this research show that 36.3% of students' revealed lower average scores in mathematics, while a significant percentage (53%) obtained lowest grades (E) in chemistry in terms of academic performance. 67.71 % of the students acknowledged a positive relationship between their mathematical skills and performance in chemistry despite their lower grades in chemistry, indicating the important aspect of mathematics in understanding chemistry concepts. The obstacles revealed, including less from parents and difficulty in quick understanding of mathematical concepts, call for the need to increase parental involvement and training in effective methods of teaching. Ejuchegahi (2025) explores the relationship between parental involvement and students' academic achievement in Ibadan Metropolis, Nigeria. It examines home-based activities, school based engagement, and teacher communication using data from one hundred and twenty(120)parents. Analyzed through Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Multiple Regression Analysis, results show a significant positive relationship between parental involvement and academic performance, with teacher communication being the strongest predictor. Parental involvement accounted for 25.5% of performance variance. The study underscores the importance of collaboration between parents, teachers, and schools, recommending strategies to enhance engagement and improve student outcomes, offering valuable insights for educators and policymakers

METHOD

Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive research design. Nworgu (2015) defined co-relational design as a type of research that tries to determine the relationship between two or more variables.. The rationale for adopting this design is to determine the extent to which identity crisis relates with adolescent's psycho-social development in study area.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprises 21,272 senior secondary school students in the 269 public senior secondary schools in Anambra State. Senior secondary school students is made up of 9550 males and 11722 females from the 269 public senior secondary schools in Anambra state. The information was

gathered from the post primary school service commission, Awka 2025. The decision to use this population is because the researcher noticed the high commitment of parents and teachers in education of their children and high rate of juvenile delinquency activities going on in the area.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample size for the study will consist of 350 SS2 students in Anambra State. Simple random sampling technique was used to draw 172 students from Onitsha North LGA, 178 students from Anambra state, making a total of 350 students who participated in the study. the samling techniques used was simple random sampling

Instrument for Data Collection

Three instruments was used for data collection, the researcher structured questionnaire titled effect of identity crisis on adolescent’s psycho-social development (ICAPD) in Senoir secondary schools in Anambra State. The respondents respond to the instrument using the following codes

- Strongly Agree SD (4)
- Agreed A (3)
- Disagreed D (2)
- Strongly disagree SD (1)

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected for the study was analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. All data collected was analysed using SPSS Version 26.

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

This chapter dealt with presentation, analysis of results and summary of major findings.

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

QUES 1; *What is the relationship between parental involvement and adolescent’s psycho-social development in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Mean rating of parental involvement and adolescent’s psycho-social development in Anambra State

S/N	Item Statements	SA	A	SD	D	SVD	MEAN	REMARK
1	My parents encourage me to try to find the reason for the mistakes I make	271	52	10	14	2.27	4.71	Accepted
2	My parents encourage me to do extra work to learn new things.	165	150	15	17	1.17	4.66	Accepted
3	My parents pay close attention to my improvement and development at home and in school.	217	93	14	23	1.11	4.85	Accepted
4	My parents try to find out and assist me on what I want to become	151	133	27	35	1.21	4.07	Accepted
5	My parents encourage me that working hard is solution to successful life	124	158	28	37	1.10	4.72	Accepted
6	When I bring home a test or paper result, my parents ask first what grade do I receive	155	155	25	52	1.13	3.85	Accepted
7	My parents pay close attention to every one of my performances at home and in school.	166	107	32	42	1.19	3.60	Accepted
8	When I am making a lot of mistakes on a task, My parents encourage me to keep trying.	151	133	27	35	1.18	3.65	Accepted
9	My parents congratulate me when I perform better than others.	114	166	28	37	1.98	3.74	Accepted
10	My parents try to get themselves engaged in every activity I am involved in.	178	105	28	36	1.12	3.99	Accepted
Cumulative Mean		= 3.5						

Table 1 revealed that there is relationship between parental involvement and adolescent's psycho-social development in Anambra State, as the cumulative response mean of 2.6 was less than the decision mean of 3.4. The implication of this result is that, parental involvement helps adolescent's psycho-social development in Anambra State. Also, the respondents agree strongly with all the ten items tested on this research question has the high response mean

Research Question 2; *What is the relationship between fatalistic belief and adolescent's psycho-social development in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Mean rating of fatalistic belief and adolescent's psycho-social development in Anambra State

S/N	Item Statements	SA	A	SD	D	SVD	MEAN	REMARK
1	If bad things happen, it is because they were meant to happen	150	127	37	33	1.25	3.89	Accepted
2	Life is very unpredictable, and there is nothing one can do to change the future	207	92	24	24	1.878	3.44	Accepted
3	If something bad is going to happen to me, it will happen to me no matter what I do	98	181	36	32	1.434	3.60	Accepted
4	There is no sense in planning a lot; if something good is going to happen, it will	114	166	30	37	1.689	3.45	Accepted
5	I feel that when good things happen, they happen as a result of my own efforts	134	177	17	19	1.34	3.18	Accepted
6	Everything that happens to a person was planned by God	159	138	24	26	1.15	3.58	Accepted
7	Whatever happens to me in my life, it is because God wanted it to happen	127	144	49	27	2.21	4.17	Accepted
8	God controls everything good and bad that happens to a person	165	122	29	31	2.51	4.21	Accepted
9	When I get what I want, it's usually because I am lucky	129	146	39	33	1.257	4.74	Accepted
10	The really good things that happen to me are mostly because of luck	190	126	15	16	1.215	4.89	Accepted
Cumulative Mean		= 3.3						

Table 2 revealed that there is relationship between fatalistic belief and adolescent's psycho-social development in Anambra State, as the cumulative response mean of 2.6 was less than the decision mean of 3.3. The implication of this result is that, fatalistic belief helps adolescent's psycho-social development in Anambra State. Also, the respondents agree strongly with all the ten items tested on this research question has the high response mea

4.2 Hypotheses Testing

The five null hypotheses formulated for this study were tested using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis one: Parental involvement does not relate with adolescent’s psycho-social development in Anambra State.

Table 3: Summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Statistics on the mean ratings of parental involvement and adolescent’s psycho-social development in Anambra State

Status	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-ratio	F-critical	Prob.
Between Groups	.640	2	.640	4.205	3.15	.001
Within Groups	721.167	345	1.374			
Total	721.806	347				

Table 3 showed the f-ratio value of (4.205) at 2 df 557 and at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The critical value (3.15) is less than f-ratio value (4.205), the probability level of significance P(.001) is less than 0.05. This means that there is significant difference in the mean ratings of the parental involvement and adolescent’s psycho-social development in Anambra State . Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis Two: Fatalistic belief does not relate with adolescent’s psycho-social development Anambra State.

Table 4: Summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Statistics on the mean ratings of fatalistic belief and adolescent’s psycho-social development in Anambra State

Status	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-ratio	F-critical	Prob.
Between Groups	1.516	2	1.516	8.163	3.15	.000
Within Groups	684.450	345	1.304			
Total	685.966	347				

Table 4 showed the f-ratio value of (8.163) at 2 df 557 and at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The critical value (3.15) is less than f-ratio value (8.163), the probability level of significance P(.000) is less than 0.05. This means that there is significant difference in the mean ratings of fatalistic belief and adolescent’s psycho-social development in Anambra State. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The findings of this study highlight the significance of parental involvement and fatalistic beliefs as critical correlates of adolescent psycho-social development in Anambra State. Adolescence is a formative stage characterized by identity exploration, emotional regulation, social integration, and the development of self-concept. Within this context, parental involvement emerges as a positive and indispensable factor that provides adolescents with emotional support, guidance, and a sense of security. When parents are actively engaged in the educational, social, and emotional lives of their children, they not only foster resilience and positive coping mechanisms but also enhance the overall psychosocial competence of adolescents. Conversely, the absence of adequate parental involvement has the potential to expose adolescents to negative peer influence, low self-esteem, academic challenges, and maladaptive social behaviors. The combined influence of parental involvement and fatalistic belief underscores the dual role of family and cultural orientation in shaping adolescent outcomes. Adolescents whose parents are supportive, communicative, and encouraging are more likely to counteract the negative influence of

fatalistic beliefs, thereby enhancing their psychological and social well-being. Conversely, those from homes with minimal parental engagement may be more vulnerable to internalizing fatalistic ideas, which can impede their psycho-social maturity.

From a policy and practical standpoint, the study emphasizes the need for parents, educators, community leaders, and policymakers in Anambra State to strengthen awareness on the benefits of consistent parental involvement while discouraging extreme fatalistic orientations that limit adolescent potential. School-based programs, community sensitization, and family counseling initiatives should be prioritized to equip parents with skills to support their children's psychosocial growth and to help adolescents adopt healthier worldviews that promote resilience, responsibility, and personal agency.

In conclusion, the psycho-social development of adolescents in Anambra State is intricately linked to the level of parental involvement and the degree to which fatalistic beliefs are internalized. For sustainable youth development, there is a need to strike a balance between preserving cultural identity and promoting adaptive beliefs that empower adolescents to take active roles in shaping their future. Thus, by fostering strong parental engagement and reducing reliance on fatalistic thinking, adolescents in Anambra State will be better positioned to navigate the complexities of modern society and emerge as socially responsible, psychologically stable, and productive citizens.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made

Evolving from the results and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations have been put forward;

- i. The findings of the study have proven that fatalistic belief positively correlates with identity crisis and adolescents. Thus, it is recommended that cognitive restructuring should be used by counselling psychologists to reshape the cognition and demystify the fatalistic beliefs among adolescents.
- ii. The findings of the study have proven that parental involvement negatively correlated with identity crisis and adolescents. Thus, it is recommended that parents should get more involved in the socio-emotional development of their children by building up relationship that involves listening and empathising with their children, validating their emotions, teaching them how to regulate their feelings and teaching them how to solve problems which will help adolescents to feel that their parents are physically and emotionally engaged in helping them to figure out their weaknesses and how to overcome identity related problem thereby drastically reducing identity crisis.

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